

THE STUDY OF WAYS OF EXPRESSING THE CATEGORY OF CASE

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Abstract. this article discusses about the study of ways of expressing the category of case on the material of the novel by O.Wilde "Portrait of Dorian Gray" and analyzes the category of case in examples.

Keywords: case, nominal, morphological category, grammatical category, genitive case, common case.

The concept of case is one of the main inflectional categories of nominal parts of speech - noun, adjective, and pronoun, numeral. Since antiquity, in the traditional sense, case has been a morphological category, since we can only talk about different cases if a word has formal differences in different cases.

The case can be defined as "a grammatical category of a name expressing its syntactic relations to other words of the utterance or to the utterance as a whole, as well as a separate grammar of this category" [1].

Recall that this theory is expressed through the opposition of two opposed grammatical forms: the first form, the genitive case, is a strong member of the opposition and is marked with the postpositive formant "-s" after the apostrophe in the singular and just an apostrophe in the plural. The second, unmarked form represents a weak member of the opposition and is usually called the "common case" form. The category of case is fully realized in the English language by animate nouns, and by limited inanimate nouns, hence the name - "theory of limited case".

Let's pay attention directly to the examples. So, in accordance with this theory, about 80 examples were analyzed. To begin with, let's focus on the implementation of the category of case with animate nouns. There were especially many examples with proper names. Some examples are given below:

1. And how delightful other people's emotions were!
2. Dorian's whims are laws to everybody, except himself.
3. As they entered the studio, Dorian Gray put his hands upon Lord Henry's arm.
4. Basil Hallward's compliments of friendship

5. Besides, I always deal with Dartmoor's tradesman, and consequently they never bother me.
 6. He is the last Lord Kelso's grandson.
 7. So, that was the story of Dorian Gray's parentage.
 8. I have to call for my husband at the club, to take him to some absurd meeting at Willis's Rooms, where he is going to be in the chair.
 9. I like Wagner's music better than anybody's.
 10. I always hear Harry's views from his friends.
 11. How different he was now from the shy, frightened boy he had met in Basil Hallward's studio!
 12. As he left the room, Lord Henry's heavy eyelids drooped, and he began to think.
 13. Dorian Gray's soul had turned to this white girl and bowed in worship before her.
 14. He hated his mother's affectations.
 15. But think of Doryan's birth, and wealth.
 16. I have been right, Basil, haven't I, to take my love out of poetry, and to find my wife in Shakespeare's plays?
 17. It was the girl's fault, not his.
 18. At any rate, he listen to those subtle, poisonous theories that in Basil Hallward's garden had first stirred within him the passion for impossible things.
 19. He leaped to his feet, tearing his hands away from Lord Henry's grasp.
 20. You can come to my sister's box.
 21. And when a woman finds that out about her husband, she either becomes dreadfully dowdy, or wears very smart bonnets that some other woman's husband has to pay for.
 22. Do you go down and see the girl's mother?
 23. I met Lady Gwendolen, Harry's sister, for the first time.
 24. I may mention that she was not the woman's only child.
 25. It is all Harry's influence.
 26. A cry of terror broke from Dorian Gray's lips, and he rushad between the painter and the screen.
 27. He was determined to find out Basil Hallward's mystery. [2]
- Significantly fewer cases of using this formant with inanimate nouns were found. Here are examples of some of them:

1. I sometimes think, Harry, that there are only two eras of any impotence in the world's history.

2. You might have entered a solicitor's office.
3. A sailor's existence was dreadful.
4. The scene was the hall of Capulet's house, and Romeo in his pilgrim's dress had entered with Mercutio and his other friends.
5. Let me have some money for my night's lodging. [2]

There were cases of closure (a type of subordinate connection in which an affix or service word, semantically referring to the core word, is placed at the first word of the phrase, thereby combining both simple and complex phrases into a single whole.), which included adverbs, possessive and indefinite pronouns, adjectives:

1. He found that he had passed his aunt's some distance, and, smiling to himself, turned back.
2. It belonged to Basil's best period.
3. It was Dorian Gray's own face that he was looking at!
4. The harsh intervals and shrill discords of barbaric music stirred him at times when Schubert's grace and Chopin's beautiful sorrows.
5. Lord Henry's casual questioning had made him lose his nerves for the moment, and he wanted his nerve still.
6. Two red sparks flashed for a moment in the woman's sodden eyes, then flickered out, and left them dull and glazed. [2].

An example of using this formant in the plural was found:

1. And so, for a whole year, he sought to accumulate the most exquisite specimens that he could find of textile and embroidered work, getting the dainty Delhl muslins, finely wrought, with gold-thread palmates, and stritched over with iridescent beetles' wings. [2].

Summing up, we can conclude that the theory of the limited case finds its confirmation. This theory adheres to the definition that case is a morphological category where the relations of nouns in a sentence should be transmitted by changing the form of the noun itself. The formant "- ' s" changes the form of the noun. A noun with this formant is defined as "the genitive or possessive case". In most cases, "- ' s" is used with animate nouns, and with inanimate nouns, the preposition of is more often used. This formant can be used both with singular nouns and with plural nouns. It is possible to use it with pronouns.

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